

Universiti Brunei Darussalam

BB-2208

Human Resource Management

Individual Assignment 2

Title:

Case analysis of Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise using Standard Causal-Model

Work by:

19B1022

Due date:

11th November 2020

Contents

1. Abstract / Executive Summary.....	3
2. Problem Statement	4
3. Case Analysis	5
4. Alternative Solutions.....	9
5. Recommendations	11

1. Abstract / Executive Summary

Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise is a paddy farming company owned by Hairinshah Haji Tahirudin. On the 4th October 2016, the business was officially registered as Hairinshah has been consistently passionate to pursue agripreneurship in paddy farming. In 2015 at 40 years of age, he applied in a programme called Belia Berpadi Programme and along the courses, he learned formal education on agricultural development that later helped him in the business such as how to utilize the rice husks, manage seeds and learn how to produce healthy rice crops. He undergoes many challenges as an agripreneurship mainly in terms of insufficient financial supports. However, his motivations help him to keep going because of his passion as he grew up in a family of farmers and in the future, he wishes to expand his business in growing vegetables and fruits. Hairinshah recommend that in order to improve the paddy farming industry, the Government needs to consider in providing the basic equipment in a serious manner as the process of harvesting the yield rely heavily on a good maintenance farm. In order to improve his business that focus on paddy farming, the recommended model to further enhance the business is called the Causal-Model relationship. This model claimed that by adopting good human resource practices, it will lead to certain outcomes and improve in organizational performance.

2. Problem Statement

According to Musa, Pg Hj Idris, & Basir (2020), there are four key issues arising from case analysis that includes lack of financial assistance, the quality of soil and its sustainability for farming, insufficiency of proper infrastructure and it is time consuming to do all the labour. Lack of financial assistance is always the main challenge for most start-up businesses as it is crucial to have enough capital. As an agripreneurship, Hairinshah needed to purchase necessary machines and supplies to support his business. Later, he received help from Youth Development Centre that offers a micro-grant of \$2,000 and Hairinshah also gets help from LiveWIRE. However, Hairinshah should not solely depend on the government's help as he needs to find other alternatives to find capital for his business.

Apart from that, quality of soil has always been important as a paddy farmer because it will affect their cultivation process. No proper examination of the soil is another issue that is experienced by Hairinshah and other agripreneurs that work on paddy farming industry. The granted land for farming is not always guaranteed to be suitable for paddy farming and this process of choosing and preparing land for farming has been inefficient. The reason for this is due to not having skills in choosing and examining the potential land to be granted to the farmers.

Another issue that is faced by Hairinshah is the insufficiency of infrastructure as it is very crucial to acquire the right water pump or irrigation and drainage systems. Without having enough and proper water supply, the rice paddy will fail to cultivate and produce. Although the land is granted to the farmers by the government, they do not provide the systems needed by the farmers and it was too expensive to be purchased by a startup agripreneur.

The last issue that arises from the case is, if Hairinshah is the one who toil and do all the labour work, it will be time consuming and burdensome for him. The cultivation of rice paddy will be delayed too. Due to this, Hairinshah is determined to employ some Indonesian labourers, but hiring them will be too costly. Thus, this is why he wishes for more participation among Bruneian youth in paddy cultivation because most paddy farmers rely heavily on foreign workers.

3. Case Analysis

There are potential solutions for problems stated that are arising in Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise.

Lack of financial assistance in Hairinshah's business is due to insufficient capital for the business. In this case, Hairinshah should not solely depend on the government's help and find other alternatives to find capital. For example, save some funds for preparation in the future in case there is no assistance from the Government or any other agency. There are also other ways to acquire capital such as through crowd funding and source funds by winning and participating in contests.

In terms of quality of the soil and its sustainability, the potential solution for this is the person that is in charge of preparing the land needs to receive a formal and basic education regarding the quality of soil, whether it is sustainable for farming or otherwise. In addition, the paddy farmer should have the right to check and examine the land first before it is officially being granted to them for cultivation.

Apart from that, insufficiency of proper infrastructure is also an issue that concerns the farmers. In this situation, the government should be aware and at least provide the basic infrastructure and machine with a proper system for paddy farmers as most of them do not come from affluent backgrounds. By helping them, this will help startup agripreneurs to flourish and succeed in the future as they will contribute back to their country. If Hairinshah has no other choice and does not want to depend on the government, another solution is to purchase second-hand machinery that cost less than the brand-new machinery or rent the machinery from rental services. By having the necessary machinery for farming such as paddy rice field irrigation machine and water pump machine, this will help him to build the infrastructure. This will also be able to help him in the future as he already buys machines that will surely help him in rice cultivation, rather than hiring experts to build for him every time as this will be too costly.

Besides, Hairinshah stated that it is too expensive to employ foreign workers to work with him in rice farming. One potential solution for this is to hire his family members or relatives that are

interested in rice farming, this will help to increase local workers and at the same time they are able to learn and adapt new skills on rice cultivation in paddy farms.

This case can be analysed by using the Causal-Model relationship. Causal model relationship is a model that represents and illustrates how human resource activities that are aligned with the strategy of an organization are able to create a greater business performance. As claimed by this model, human resources will only be successful if the strategy is aligned along with the business strategy in line accompanied by the best-fit-theory. Thus, the strategy of Human Resource is obtained from the overall strategy in the organization so that maximum performance financial is acquired (“The Standard Causal Model of HRM,” n.d.).

The causal-model can be illustrated below.

Source: (“The Standard Causal Model of HRM,” n.d.).

It shows that the overall strategy of the business that aligned with the Human Resource strategy will develop the HR practices. This will eventually lead to HR outcomes where it will improve the internal performance and at the same time enhancing the financial performance.

The Causal-Model relationship can be applied into Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise. Below is the illustration of the Causal-Model relationship of Agrotex Global Success Enterprise.

Causal-Model of Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise

The process of human resource practices influences HRM outcomes which will also influence the business performance is called indirect linkage or also known as mediated HRM effect.

As can be seen from the model, if Hairinshah wants to hire workers to work with him, he can improve the induction process. For example, Hairinshah can adopt interactive learning when hiring new employees as it is one of the greatest ways and this will create an interesting training for the potential employees (Rtvadmin, 2019). In addition to that, Hairinshah can apply online recruitment as people will become attracted to it and this helps to save time because people will respond directly (Reddy, 2018). Another HR practice is through training where Hairinshah can exchange knowledge with other experienced paddy farmers. Based on the case study, Awang Lau How Teck who is the manager of Syarikat Tunas Harapan is the role model of Hairinshah as he is inspired by him and has been a mentor to other agripreneurs. As a mentor, Hairinshah can learn more knowledge and skills from Awang Lau Teck and exchange knowledge between them. Hairinshah will receive knowledge regarding the quality of the soil too before choosing the right farm for him. This will eventually lead to improved guidance to Hairinshah as the owner of the company and this will enhance the business performance.

Other than that, if Hairinshah participates in different programs or contests, this will help him to improve communications skills, more involvement that is able to build up his confidence, and more future development opportunities. By joining more programs and contests, this will help him to gather more funds and be able to help and assist him in financial matters. He also has the opportunities to build proper infrastructure to achieve high quality rice with the right water pump or irrigation and drainage systems.

After adapting all the human resource management practices, it will result in the human resource management (HRM) outcomes. If Hairinshah uses interactive learning in recruitment and selection as well as to train the employees, this will help to reduce cost and lead to substantial cost savings. On the other hand, by having training and knowledge exchange among the owner as well as the employees, this will result in increased employee commitment as the employees feel valuable and they contribute a significant role in the company. The employee's intention to quit will be reduced and lead to low labour turnover. Hairinshah will be able to improve his skills and knowledge if he has a mentor and is involved in the coaching program. This will help to guide him towards a better owner of the business and he will be able to improve the management of his company. HRM outcomes will then contribute to the organizational performance.

Other than indirect linkage, there is also a direct linkage that starts from HR practices directly to organizational performance, which is also called an unmediated HRM effect. This process indicates that HR practices will have direct influences on organizational performance. For example, if the company adapts the right process of recruitment and selection, this will lead to improvement in internal performance such as increase in employment as many people are interested to join the company. When there is a participation implemented in HR practices, the organization will benefit as both Hairinshah and employees are able to develop their skills in managing the business.

The last link in the model is known as reversed causality which means that only high-performance business can afford human resource practices. Therefore, the performance result makes accessible to the business the potential to apply HR interventions. However, since Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise is still considered as a small firm, this link still cannot be applied but may be useful in the future.

4. Alternative Solutions: Pros and cons of possible solutions to problems

Pros of possible solutions to problems:

Joining contests such as paddy farming contests can help to boost Hairinshah's confidence as well as his knowledge and skills. This will also help to contribute more to his funds and enhance his business reputation. He able to gain credibility among his potential customers as he proved to be skillful and experienced. In addition, if Hairinshah is able to receive crowdfunding, it will be very efficient as a start-up compared to seeking for a loan that might put him in a debt situation that will affect his business in bad ways ("The Benefits of Crowdfunding," n.d.).

As for the quality of soil, the person who in charge of choosing the farm should receive formal education and this will help the farming industry in Brunei to flourish as both the provider and receiver care about the quality. This will also lead to quality local products and help to increase the Gross domestic product (GDP) of the country. Additionally, if the paddy farmer is given the rights to check the quality of the soil, the farmer will benefit from it and be able to produce more. The farmers will have a sense of involvement and feel encouraged to do better in their business.

If the business does not have proper infrastructure, Hairinshah can go to rental services and rent the machine that can help to build infrastructure. The benefits of using rental equipment is there will be no repair costs as Hairinshah is not the one who is responsible for the maintenance and repairs and he is able to try the machine and see how it works before he buys it (Small Business Expert, 2019). Other than renting the equipment, Hairinshah also can purchase the second-hand machine as one of the well-known benefits is it is more affordable than the new one and it can save a lot of money. If comparison is to be made between the performance of a new machine and second-hand model, there is not much difference. This is because sometimes the second-hand machinery works really well with an affordable cost (John, 2019).

Hairinshah also mentioned that it is too expensive in employing foreign workers. By hiring his family members or relatives, this will make things easier as both the owner and the employees know each other well and have a good chemistry and create a harmonious environment.

Cons of possible solution to problems:

Winning a contest might not be so helpful in raising funds as the cash prizes provided will not be enough to support his business. Joining and hoping to win in a contest is not easy as there will be countless talented agripreneurs that will act as competitors. On the other hand, if Hairinshah succeeds in gathering the crowdfunding but in the end, if his business is at risk of failure or not going as planned, this will damage the reputation and it will be hard to recover it (Johansson, 2018). Thus, the customer and potential customer may not be interested in buying the products.

The cons for the solution of where the person in charge needs to receive basic education on the quality of soil is not guaranteed and not in the control of the farmer's hand. In addition, not every farmer granted their rights to check the quality of the soil as the provider may not have the time to entertain each of the farmer's requests. Furthermore, there might be limited quality lands that are available in the country.

One of the issues in renting equipment is sometimes people do not check the machine thoroughly that in some occasions the reliability and the quality is not guaranteed as there might be some damages (Petersson, 2014). Besides, purchasing second-hand machinery will consume too much time as Hairinshah needs to do thorough research and negotiate the price with the sellers in order to choose the best equipment (Cambridge Entrepreneur Academy, 2019).

In addition, working with family members can also cause conflicts and misunderstanding if Hairinshah is unable to handle and manage this problem well.

5. Recommendations

Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise is a paddy farming based that aims to provide quality local products and Hairinshah also targets to expand his business in the future. Farming jobs have always relied heavily on good infrastructure and equipment such as machines for water pumps and drainage systems. In this case, the most optimal solution based on the problems that arise and by looking at the alternative solutions is by considering buying second-hand machinery either by using his own money or getting help through crowdfunding. This has the most obvious benefits as it will help Hairinshah to own his own proper machine to build infrastructure for paddy farming at lower price and this will also have positive impacts on the overall costs and expenses. Owning proper machines will help to improve his business in terms of better quality and able to produce in big quantities. Good reputation of his business can also be achieved through this and help to increase his sales. This will also lead to addressing other issues as this will assist him in financial support and he is able to employ workers to work with him. Thus, this is the optimal solution for the business as this will be the most profitable and at the same time provide the least cost for the business. By the time his business able to expand and succeed, he can buy more expensive machines and upgrade his business performance. The advice from Hairinshah to young Bruneians is do not be afraid of taking risks in a business as it is one of the good characteristics of an entrepreneur.

References:

- Cambridge Entrepreneur Academy. (2019). Pros and Cons of Buying Secondhand Farm Equipment. Retrieved November 10, 2020, from <https://www.cambridgeentrepreneuracademy.com/pros-and-cons-of-buying-used-farm-equipment/>
- Johansson, A. (2018). The Advantages and Disadvantages of Crowdfunding for Entrepreneurs. Retrieved November 10, 2020, from <https://startupnation.com/start-your-business/advantages-disadvantages-crowdfunding/>
- John, S. (2019). What are the Major Benefits of Buying Used Farm Equipment? Retrieved November 10, 2020, from <https://medium.com/@sarahjohn99888/what-are-the-major-benefits-of-buying-used-farm-equipment-2e593267848f>
- Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.
- Petersson, A. (2014). Advantages and Disadvantages of Renting Business Equipment. Retrieved November 10, 2020, from <https://medium.com/@albertpetersson/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-renting-business-equipment-9624fd00a381>
- Reddy, K. (2018). How to Reduce Recruitment Costs? 12 Super Effective Ways. Retrieved November 10, 2020, from <https://content.wisestep.com/reduce-recruitment-costs/>
- Rtvadmin. (2019). 10 Ways to Improve Your Induction Process. Retrieved November 10, 2020, from <https://res.digital/10-ways-to-improve-your-induction-process/>
- Small Business Expert. (2019). The Top 10 Benefits of Rental Equipment. Retrieved November 10, 2020, from https://www.catrentalstore.com/en_US/blog/top-benefits-renting-equipment.html
- The Benefits of Crowdfunding. (n.d.). Retrieved November 10, 2020, from <https://www.fundable.com/learn/resources/guides/crowdfunding/the-benefits-of-crowdfunding>

The Standard Causal Model of HRM. (n.d.). Retrieved November 09, 2020, from <https://www.peoplehum.com/glossary/the-standard-causal-model-of-hrm>